

Study of Organo Halide Perovskite Absorber Layer in performance of solar cells

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ABSTRACT

Due to their high efficiency and low cost of manufacture, single junction solar cells with perovskite absorbers and front and back electrodes offer excellent photoelectric properties. The use of a lead-free perovskite absorber layer in solar cell PSC composition promotes industrial application, thus the quest for environmentally safe and non-toxic perovskite solar cell PSC composition with the highest possible efficiency is being studied in various materials around the world. In this work, the solar cell capacitance simulator (SCAPS) is used to provide a comprehensive research for achieving greater energy conversion capacity of lead-free tin (Ge) based perovskite as an absorber layer. The understanding and appropriateness of TiO₂ as an electron transport layer (ETL), CH₃NH₃GeI₃ as a perovskite absorber layer, and Mo as a hole transport layer (HTL) have been conferred. The PCE achieved in this work for an optimized parameter is found to be the best possible value of 12.54% with an FF of 83.5% has been achieved for this configuration of PSC at 300K other electrical parameter like V_{oc} And J_{sc} are found to be 0.925V and 17.518 mA/cm². The ETL, HTL, and absorber thicknesses are optimized to be 0.033μm, 0.2143μm, and 4.4 μm, respectively, which is the optimized value for maximum FF % and efficiency due to the generation of additional charge carriers under standard operating conditions

Keywords: PSC ; ETL ; HTL , SCAPS

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1. Introduction

The transition of sunlight into electrical energy is done by a device named SC. In 1839, Edmond Becquerel gave the idea of SC. When exposed to daylight, he observed that

brass metal produced a continuous current. Later on, in the 1870s, W. Smith, W. G. Adams, and R. E. Day determined a Photovoltaic effect in Se. Later on, it has been found that when we placed a sheet of selenium covered with transparent gold leaf film. He obtained the result in which there is continuous production of current and broad force. The problem is that at that time no theory explains the process of conversion of sunlight into electrical energy. At that Time German scientist Werner Siemens verified this concept and conclude that selenium converts sunlight into electricity but at that time the efficiency of Photovoltaic cells is less than 1% [1].

Various photovoltaic cells in a built-in group, all oriented in one plane, represent a photovoltaic panel or photovoltaic module. The front side of the solar panel is exposed to sunlight laminated with pieces of glass for the protection of solar wafers. SCs are generally connected in series or parallel circuits [2].

The kinds of SCs are listed below based on generations

- The 1st generation cells are called conventional ordinary cells and are composed of crystalline silicon i.e. mono crystalline and poly crystalline SCs.
- The 2nd generation cells are made up of amorphous silicon, CdTe, and CIGS cells commercially huge in Domestic level photovoltaic electric power plants, establishing built-in photovoltaic or in small power Houses [3].

Nano crystal-based, Polymer-based Perovskite, Dye sensitized, and concentrated SCs are examples of third-generation SCs

Perovskite SCs emerge out in the PV cell market in a very short time. Initially, the PSC has an output of 2.2% in 2006. In 2011, the Pout of Perovskite SC is 6.5%. Later on, in 2014 the output of perovskite SC is reported as 17.9%. The SC named perovskite after the Russian mineralogist Lev. A. perovski (1792-1856). The chemical formula of the material is CaTiO_3 . The overall equation for the minerals is ABX_3 , X denotes the anion where A and B are the cations, are called perovskites. The worth of A is more remarkable than the B. In PV cells, Organic-inorganic perovskite are utilized. In ABX_3 , A is the bigger cation typically methyl ammonium (CH_3NH^+) is utilized. Where X is halogen, ordinarily utilized as iodine, chlorine, or bromine. The B contains lead while metal can likewise be used [4].

The main property of the perovskite solar is that it has the ability to absorb maximum incident light. Usually, the high efficiency perovskite cells contains lead. The problem is that Pb is toxic material. Secondly the problem is that there is degradation of cells due to UV rays.

The first perovskite SC was made in 2009 and the efficiency of that cell was 3.9%. This was made by a combination of dye-sensitized SC with a layer of perovskite material on titanium oxide.

In 2011, the performance of PSC is improved from 3.8% to 6.5%. This is done with the help of quantum dots for Nano crystalline materials [5].

2. Materials and Methods

SCAPS is 1-D stimulated program developed at electronics and information system department of the University of Gent, Belgium. The first thin film devised for polycrystalline cell structures designed for the CuInSe_2 and CdTe series accommodates multiple interfaces and large band gap. The package has been developed over the years to include multiple improvements in the user interface, including additional mechanisms such as tunnelling, Auger recombination. The original program was developed for the cellular structure of the CuInSe_2 and CdT families. This program can now be applied to

crystalline SCs and amorphous batteries with recent developments with recent developments, this program can now be applied to crystalline SCs and amorphous batteries.

SCAPS is a Windows-oriented program, prepared with Lab Windows/CVI of National Instruments.

Figure 1: SCAPS Action panel

The basic actions have their own dedicated panels:

1. Run SCAPS.
2. Mark out the problem, including the configuration, material and all of your SCs characteristics.
3. Generate the checklist of the conditions under which you want to run simulation, i.e. the working point
4. Specify what you've been working on, i.e. which measurement you will be modelling.
5. Begin your computations
6. Show the curves that have been stimulated

Run SCAPS:

On your desktop click the shortcut icon, or in your file manager double-tap the scaps3200.exe file in the action panel SCAPS starts.

Set Problem:

Choose load in the bottom end of the panel which opens by tapping the set problem button in the action panel. Choose and explore e.g. the file NUMOS CIGS baseline.def: Which is the practicum session example problem file. The file exist in folder SCAPS def., where SCAPS refers to the SCAPS installation dictionary and where the SCAPS .exe file resides. Search for that file if necessary. By tapping set problem in the action panel at a later time, you can change all of the cells settings.

Define the working point:

The working point describes the variables that are suitable for this measurement and are not changed during the measurement simulation.

- T temperature: can be used for all types of measurement. Note that the only variables with an obvious relationship on temperature: in SCAPS are NC (T), NV (T), thermal velocities, thermal voltage kT and all their derivatives. You must manually add the associated material characteristics..
- The voltage V: is overlooked in both IV and CV simulation. SCAPS always initiate at zero Volt, and progresses to the desire voltage in a series of steps that you can additionally stipulate.
- The frequency f: is discarded in I-V.
- The illumination: This is the light source that is used for all measurements. It determines bias light conditions For QE measurements. The options are dark or light, the choice of light illuminates, and the spectrum is selected. The standard is to Light a sun (1000 wb/m^2) with universal 'air volume 1.5, worldwide, but you can do it otherwise. For your targeted simulations you will need a wide spectrum of monochromatic light and spectra. If you have an optical emulator you can download a generation configuration that is also a change with spectrum

Select the measurement to stimulate

You can replicate one or more of the measures IV, CV, Cf and QE in the actions portion of the action panel. If necessary, change the arguments start and finish values, as well as the number of steps. It starts by running one stimulation at a time and using some quite primitive methods. It's possible that your computer and SCAPS programme are slower than you believe, or that the issue is more complex to solve. You don't have to define the CV simulation IV curve because it is calculated automatically.

Figure 2: SCAPS cell definition panel

Starts the Calculations:

Click the [Calculation: Single Shot] button in the Actions panel. The panel of energy band opens and the calculation commences. A status bar is appears at the bottom of the panel. For example "IV from 0.00 to 0.70V: V = 0.650V", Indicates how the simulation will proceed. On the other hand, SCAPS is giving a free introduction to how the conduction and valence bands Fermi levels are evolving. There is, but do not exaggerate. Anyway, you won't lose the already calculated IV points.

Device simulation:

We used SCAPS-1D version (3.3.08) to simulate the AM 1.5 sun spectrum with 100mW/cm2 light intensity, 300K room temperature, and standard parameters. It was carried out as follows. It is a well-known window-based modelling programme first created by the Faculty of Electronic Engineering, Ghent University, Belgium, for thin-film polycrystalline layers with many interfaces. Three separate governing equations are used in the model's algorithm.

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial x^2} = -\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} = -\frac{p}{\epsilon_s} \dots\dots\dots 4.1$$

$$= -\frac{q}{\epsilon_s} [p - n + N_d^+ - N_a^- \pm N_{def}] \dots\dots\dots 4.2$$

Where Ψ , ϵ_s , q , e , n represents electrostatic potential, static relative permittivity, charge, electrons and holes respectively, N_d and N_a represents donor acceptor densities respectively, and N_{def} is the donor.

The equation for the carrier continuity of the device can be expressed as:

$$-\frac{\partial j_p}{\partial x} + G - U_p(n, p) = 0 \dots\dots\dots 4.3$$

$$-\frac{\partial j_n}{\partial x} + G - U_n(n, p) = 0 \dots\dots\dots 4.4$$

In addition, the equations for carrier current density are:

$$j_p = qn\mu_p E - qD_p \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \dots\dots\dots 4.5$$

$$j_n = qn\mu_n E + qD_n \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} \dots\dots\dots 4.6$$

Where q is the charge, μ_p and μ_n are carrier mobilities, and D_p and D_n are the diffusivity.

Over a wide temperature range, you may determine photovoltaic and electrical characteristics such as J_{sc} , V_{oc} , Percent PCE, and FF percent, as well as values of various thicknesses. In a solar cell composition that can perform in both bright and dark settings, SCAPS-1D can contain seven structural layers. ITO and Mo are metal contacts, TiO2 is ETL, NiO is HTL, and CH₃NH₃GeI₃ is absorber layer in the proposed device configuration ITO/TiO₂/CH₃NH₃GeI₃/NiO/Mo of solar cell.

Simulation methodology:

The device structure for ITO/TiO₂/CH₃NH₃GeI₃/NiO/Mo is shown in Figure 4.1. The work functions Mo and ITO were acquired from the literature. 4.95eV for Mo and 4.65eV for ITO materials, respectively. To optimize and examine the device, we conducted conventional methods, including typical procedures. In order to enhance device performance, we also adjusted the thickness of each layer.

Figure 3: Simulated diagram of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$ -based perovskite solar cell

Results:

Optimized electrical parameters of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$ -based perovskite solar cell

To obtain ideal device characteristics, electrical parameters and thickness values of distinct layers have been extensively examined. The energy band diagram for the improved device is shown in Figure 4.2. Aside from these numbers, even minor changes in the characteristics of the added layer might have an impact on the device's performance.

Figure 4: Energy band diagram for the optimized device

A solar cell's J-V properties are seen in Fig. 4.3. The Voc 0.8036 V and Jsc 17.3523 mA/cm² were observed after adjusting the ETL/Absorber/HTL layer thickness parameters for the solar cell, which was 74.4006 percent more than the previous result. These findings were obtained by using the device's best settings.

Figure 5: J-V characteristics for the optimized CH₃NH₃GeI₃-based solar cell

The optimized energy band diagram in Figure 4.4 verifies the preceding block diagram. The energy band-gap was set to 3.8 eV for NiO, 1.9 eV for CH₃NH₃GeI₃ absorbers, and 3.2 eV for TiO₂. With rising hole and electron mobility values, the PCE percent of the CH₃NH₃GeI₃ perovskite absorber has been seen to grow.

Figure 6: Energy band diagram for optimized $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$ -based Solar cell

Higher mobility indicates higher diffusivity (D), higher J_{sc} , constant temperature, lower current density, and lower V_{oc} . PCE, on the other hand, is controlled directly. This shows that minimum electron carrier recombination is necessary for high-performance solar cells, especially in the suggested perovskite solar cell simulation, $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3/\text{TiO}_2$. The user interface was taken into consideration. Interface defect densities were numerically simulated in the range of 1.0×10^{10} to $1.0 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The impacts of variation in interface faults are depicted in Figure 4.5. It's reasonable to assume that increasing interfacial defect density enhances recombination rates, which lowers PC

Figure 7: (a) Interface Defects density vs. Electrical Parameters

Figure 8: Interface Defects density vs. Electrical Parameters

Effects of TiO2 ETL thickness

The effect of the thickness of the TiO2 on the performance of the device was investigated with SCAPS-1D. It was observed that Voc, Jsc, were reduced but FF and eta rise from start and show the maximum value at 0.003 μm. The thickness of the TiO2 layer corresponds to the layer thickness shown in Figure 4.7. The maximum values of the electrical parameters such as Voc, and eta% were recorded 0.87541 V and 11.9638 % at 0.003 μm and Jsc and FF 17.4747 mA/cm2, 82.8997 % respectively.

Figure 9: Different parameters vs. thickness of ETL

Figure 11: Carrier Generation vs. surface depth of optimized solar cell

Effects of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$ absorber layer thickness

The impact of the thickness of the $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$ on several solar cell characteristics is shown in Fig4.9. With increasing surface depth, the PCE, J_{sc} , and V_{oc} increased step by step. The highest PCE and V_{oc} were 11.824 percent, with 0.80954V corresponding to a $5\mu\text{m}$ increased light-safeguard layer thickness. The highest value of completed FF is 84.1977 percent, while J_{sc} has the lowest value of $17.27087\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. This occurs on the basis that the increased efficiency is due to the current thickness expanding as the light-absorption layer thickness expands. Because the absorber material is more accessible to light, increasing the surface depth of the absorber layer helps to improve the transporter age. More electron-opening sets are produced, and electrons are created as a result.

Figure 12: Different parameters vs. Thickness of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$

3. Discussion

In the near future, further growth in energy and power usage may result in disastrous outcomes. Recent years have seen the application of inorganic and organic halide solar cells based on perovskite. Absorbers are popular in the PV world because they have good photoelectric performance, current density, and quantum efficiency, as well as inexpensive production costs. Scientists are observing some of these traits using first-principles calculations with the DFT. Normally, organic-inorganic halide compounds may be used as active absorber materials in perovskite solar cells, and these materials can achieve efficiencies of 20% or more, however there are two major issues. The first is that these materials are made up of organic cations, which causes instability and shortens the life of perovskite materials, and the second is lead (Pb) toxicity.

PSCs based on $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{GeI}_3$ are the focus of current research, with temperature, structural layer thickness, disease density, interface flaws, service generation recombination, and power band-gap all enhancing overall tool performance. It depicts the process of becoming. The use of TiO_2 ETL layer hetero-zygotes in new configurations has been researched. It can play a major role in the overall performance of the forward stepping tool due to its excellent optical characteristics. The major purpose of our cutting-edge research is to figure out how to precisely optimize all of the PSC's functional properties, minimize manufacturing costs, and get extra PCE tools.

4. Conclusions

To determine the highest performance of perovskite solar cells, an examination of tin-based perovskite solar cells was carried out in the context of numerical simulations using SCAPS-1D software. With increased performance, a new ITO/TiO₂/CH₃NH₃GeI₃/NiO/Mo combination has been presented. The device's performance in terms of temperature and thickness has been investigated using various parameters that have been optimised. With a higher wavelength in the infrared area, the absorption of this new configuration in the visible region reduces, resulting in a reduction in cell efficiency. The best possible efficiency of 12.54% with an FF of 83.5% has been achieved for this configuration of PSC at 290K. Electrical parameter like Voc and Jsc is found to be 0.925V and 17.518 mA/cm². Input parameters were calculated through the material studio and were compared with the literature throughout the performance of perovskite solar cells at optimal value. The Eg value of CH₃NH₃GeI₃, TiO₂, and NiO are 1.9eV, 3.2eV, and 3.8eV respectively with an optimized thickness of 4.4μm, 0.033μm, and 0.2143μm respectively. Further increase in thickness layers causes a reduction in PCE. The optimized value of interface defect density is found to be 1×10¹⁴ cm⁻² for interface of CH₃NH₃GeI₃/NiO and 1×10¹⁴ cm⁻² for CH₃NH₃GeI₃/TiO₂. The highest value of electron and holes (Ge) is found to be 5.2×10²¹ cm⁻³ at the surface depth value of 5.1 μm. The total recombination of the device is lesser than the carrier's generation. Researchers will be able to construct more systematic solar for future applications with the help of this simulation of Organo-metal halide perovskite solar cells.

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Conceptualization, methodology, writing—original draft preparation, H.A, M.A.K, and S.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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